

Total Ventricle Volume M

Total Ventricle Volume F

Total Lateral Ventricle Volume Left M

Total Lateral Ventricle Volume Left F

Total Lateral Ventricle Volume Right M

Total Lateral Ventricle Volume Right F

Third Ventricle Volume M

Third Ventricle Volume F

Fourth Ventricle Volume M

Fourth Ventricle Volume F

Frontal Horn Volume Left M

Frontal Horn Volume Left F

Frontal Horn Volume Right M

Frontal Horn Volume Right F

Body Volume Left M

Body Volume Left F

Body Volume Right M

Body Volume Right F

Trigone Volume Left M

Trigone Volume Left F

Trigone Volume Right M

Trigone Volume Right F

Occipital Horn Volume Left M

Occipital Horn Volume Left F

Occipital Horn Volume Right M

Occipital Horn Volume Right F

Temporal Horn Volume Left M

Temporal Horn Volume Left F

Temporal Horn Volume Right M

Temporal Horn Volume Right F

